

THE NOTION OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT
COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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“Development and education cannot be given or passed on to anyone. Those who wish to participate must do so through their own activity, their own strength and their own efforts.

“... A person begins with self-development, not education. The latter joins the former and, in its image and likeness, can only act on its soil[7]”.

Personal development is one of the complex and multifaceted categories of pedagogy. Philosophers believe that as an active part of self-creation is based on the forces of self-motion that determine the direction of an individual's self-consciousness. This phenomenon has long been known in philosophy. The allocation of self-propulsion as a key moment in personality self-formation is characteristic of Russian philosophers and psychologists of the early twentieth century (Blonsky P.P., Wentzel K.N., Bakhtin M.M., Berdyaev N. A., Gumilyov L.N., Solovyov B.C., Florensky L.A. and etc). Modern psychologists define self-development as the primary internal mechanism of development and formation. In educational science, this term defines the essence of the process of personality development and formation in the active position of the subject. A. Comenius emphasized the principle of natural adaptation in education and saw in this the beginning of self-propulsion determining the creation of the “image of man”. V. A. Sukhomlinsky believed that a person's desire for self-development is inherent in him. The idea of self-development was researched and developed by O.S. Guzman. Guzman saw in it a fundamental force for developing a free and independent personality with the primacy of the “self”. This aspect plays a leading role in contemporary educational research (Sannikova A.I., Belkin A.S., Grigoryeva N.G., Semenov V.D., Tskerman G.A, etc.). An analysis of the literature shows that the basis of self-development is based on the self-motive force, which determines both the level and mode of expression of that power and ego. All researchers have reduced this phenomenon to the key notion of personality activity, leading to particularly rigorous studies to clarify the nature of the process of self-development. It is important for educational research that solves

problems of development, self-development, and character formation in various aspects of self-affirmation.

The interpretation of the concept of “self-development” by different authors is different, since this phenomenon is considered from different positions. Most authors come to the conclusion that self-development implies the development of certain personal and professional qualities, which takes place not at the external level, but at the level of the self, while the initiator of the process is the personality itself [1, p. 73]. “A person’s desire for self-development is due to the presence of “entelechy” — an innate tendency and ability of an individual to realize himself¹” (V. Stern) [7, p.140]. V. I. Smirnov emphasizes the role of active actions: “... it is and only a person’s own activity that is a way of his self-development, a condition for the realization of his goals[7, p.141]. The source and driving force of self-development is the need for self-development .

The course of an individual's self-development and its results are determined by two factors: a) the individual's ability to act “with knowledge of the matter”, the quality and level of education; b) the nature and measure of the embodiment of socio-cultural experience in the realities that the subject of activity deals with [8, p. 330]. Self-development is the “deployment” of already existing, but “curtailed” for the time being inclinations, abilities, skills, qualities. Self-development is a purposeful internal activity and a conscious focus on unfolding and improving properties, aspects, qualities, etc. that are significant for a person [9]. E. B. Baboshina, N. R. Bityanova and L. N. Kulikova consider self-development as a conscious process of purposeful multi-aspect personal formation and self-change of a person with the aim of self-realization based on internal significant aspirations and external influences, which should be considered through a change in self-regulation of a person [2]. The Big Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language (edited by S. A. Kuznetsov) gives the following definition of the concept of “self-development”: “The mental or physical development of a person through independent studies or exercises”. When analyzing the totality of various characteristics of the concept of "self-development" of a person, available in the literature, the following common features of these characteristics attract attention. Self-development is: 1) human value and need; 2) the result of conscious goal setting; 3) spiritual and practical activity of the individual; 4) the process of own changes; 5) a process directed towards the ideal; 6) creative process; 7) the process taking place in the

¹ Смирнов, В. И. Общая педагогика в тезисах, дефинициях, иллюстрациях. — М.: Педагогическое общество России, 2000.

communication of the individual; 8) not only unity, but also the opposition of the processes of self-development of the individual and the community; 9) the process of realization of superpersonal values; 10) a random sequence of transitions through bifurcation points due to external influences on the personality [5, p.57–58] . The process of self-development of the personality, outwardly and naturally pushed by various circumstances, is determined from the inside by the personal need for it and the spiritual aspiration of the personality with its unique history. All these factors have a real motivating force for self-development [5, p. 62]. Studies by B. G. Ananiev, K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, L. I. Antsyferova, L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev, A. R. Luria, V. S. Mukhina, S. L. Rubinshtein and others show that mastering the methods and techniques of self-development of the individual is a complex and contradictory process extended in time. At the same time, the most important conditions for its implementation are the conscious desire for balance and harmony of the individual and the surrounding world, the readiness to improve one's own personality, the ability to make decisions, commensurate them with the needs of society.

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